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Understanding Human Behaviour With Wearable Cameras Based on Information From the Human Hand

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Abstract

Hand pose estimation is one of the critical tasks in egocentric vision, as humans interact with thousands of objects with their hands every day. We discuss key factors for egocentric hand pose estimation for ma single camera and how retrieved hand skeletons can be used in applications for modelling human behaviour.

Introduction

Wearable cameras provide a unique perspective by capturing daily activities from an individual's viewpoint, an egocentric view. Placing a camera on the human body provides broad information about the wearer's life and health. Understanding human behaviour through wearable cameras can be approached in two main ways: long-term and short-term behaviour analysis. Considering an example of food intake, long-term behaviour analysis focuses on identifying individuals' routines and recurring activities, such as where and when they eat. In contrast, short-term behaviour analysis examines specific movements, determines the types of food

consumed, and estimates their nutritional content. Hands play a crucial role in most Activities of Daily Living (ADLs), such as eating, drinking, or other essential tasks and are at the centre of the egocentric image in most cases (Núñez-Marcos, Azkune, & Arganda-Carreras, 2022). These activities often involve various hand movements in relation to objects, such as rotating, picking up, or manipulating them. In short-term analysis, examining these hand-object interactions through egocentric vision provides a detailed understanding of the actions performed, offering valuable insights into both specific tasks and broader patterns of behaviour. This makes egocentric hand pose estimation a critical challenge. We consider hand pose estimation a task of localising 21 key points that describe the finger joints, palm, and wrist positions from a single camera.

Methodologies for Egocentric Hand Pose Estimation

Hand pose estimation can be understood in 2D and 3D space, each with distinct advantages. While 2D models involve less complex networks and potentially faster processing, 3D models offer a richer understanding by capturing depth. One potential solution is a single-hand approach named *EffHandNet* (Mucha & Kampel, 2024), which begins with a pre-trained hand detector that identifies regions, $R_{1,2}$ of hands in the egocentric input image. It then predicts the hand pose within $R_{1,2}$. The feature extraction is handled by Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), followed by transposed convolutions to produce heatmaps representing joints' locations. Although this method benefits from extensive datasets, its drawbacks include increased computational load due to multiple passes through the backbone network. *EffHandEgoNet* (Mucha & Kampel, 2024) addresses these limitations using an egocentric approach that hand presence in the scene, $H_{L,R}$ and employs two up-sampling heads to refine the resolution. This method improves the modelling of hand-object interactions and outputs the hand pose as 2D coordinates. Its efficiency stems from a single forward pass through the backbone, and it excels in learning interactions between hands, though the limited availability of public egocentric datasets constrains it. Extending *EffHandEgoNet* to 3D (Mucha, Wray, & Kampel, 2024) incorporates a regression module to estimate the z coordinates. This results in 2.5D coordinates in the image space. 2.5D coordinates are then transformed into 3D representation using the pinhole camera model, enabling an understanding of hand poses in three-dimensional space.

Egocentric Applications of Hand Pose

Egocentric hand pose estimation has emerged as a valuable tool across various applications, e.g., action recognition, struggle determination, and hand rehabilitation. Following (Mucha & Kampel, 2024), In action recognition, this technique involves analysing sequences of frames f_1, \dots, f_n . Actions shorter than n

frames are zero-padded, while longer ones undergo uniform subsampling. The YOLOv7 model is employed for object detection, describing objects with bounding boxes and labels. Further, the hand pose with object information is embedded with a transformer encoder and action classification layer. Experiments show a strong correlation between the accuracy of action recognition and the hand pose. In the realm of struggle determination, egocentric hand pose estimation facilitates categorising struggle levels into binary classifications. Accurate recognition of struggle is crucial for providing effective support to individuals. Recent approaches have achieved an 89% accuracy in binary struggle determination by integrating hand pose information through a transformer encoder alongside spatial-temporal features from video. Furthermore, in hand rehabilitation for stroke patients who experience hand dysfunction, egocentric vision can address challenges such as exercise recognition, repetition counting, exercise detection, and form evaluation, employing hand pose estimation (Mucha, Tanaka, & Kampel, 2024).

Conclusion

Precise pose description is fundamental for multiple applications in egocentric image processing. 2D pose information is, at this stage, more accurate as it eliminates the challenging estimation of depth and can be an alternative to 3D pose estimation when inference time is crucial. While methods based on hand detection struggle with hand pose estimation in egocentric perspectives due to occlusions, alternative approaches show that the highest precision is reached when considering both hands in the input for learning complex interactions.

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